

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Spontaneous interspecific hybrids in *Oryza* in Lao PDR

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Three wild species of rice, *Oryza rufipogon*, *O. nivara* (diploid AA genome), and *O. granulata* (diploid, GG), are found in Lao PDR. Recent reports of *O. officinalis* still need to be confirmed.

While collecting rice germplasm in four central and southern provinces, we found several *O. rufipogon* and *O. nivara* populations growing near cultivated rice (*O. sativa*) in roadside ditches, isolated ponds, canals, and in ricefields. In six populations we discovered what appeared to be intermediate forms between wild and cultivated rice (see table)—probably spontaneous hybrids or/and different progenies at segregations. The inter-

mediate forms were mixed with the wild species and cultivated rice in five populations (see figure). We observed only intermediate weedy forms, however, in one population (Thapangthong).

Flowering is synchronous in cultivated rice, making the duration short. The wild species, however, flower over a much longer period. For example, *O. nivara* (an annual) flowers in September and completes its life cycle by the end of October. *O. rufipogon* (a perennial) flowers in October and completes its life cycle in December or January of the next year. So the possibility of cultivated and wild rices hybridizing is real.

Cultivated rice is mostly self-pollinated, while in the wild species (particularly *O. rufipogon*), outcrossing has been reported to be as high as 50%. We believe the gene flow must have been from the cultivated to the wild forms. Intermediate weedy populations, such as those we identified, develop from such spontaneous hybrids.

Panicles of wild, weedy, and cultivated rice (left to right) found in a farmer's field in Salakham, Lao PDR.

Location and habitat of six hybrid populations of rice found in Lao PDR.

	Bolek population	Nongpin population	Salakham population	Mahaxai population	Thapangthong population	Samakhixai population
Province/town	Vientiane	Vientiane	Vientiane	Khammouane	Savannakhet	Attapeu
District	Xaithani	Chanthabouli	Hatsayfong	Mahaxai	Thapangthong	Samakhixai
Village	Bolek	Nongpin	Salakham	Ten	Nahuahay	Sekhman
Coordinates	18° 05' N, 103° 06' E	18° 03' N, 102° 46' E	18° 02' N, 102° 45' E	17° 28' N, 105° 15' E	15° 50' N, 105° 55' E	14° 50' N, 106° 52' E
Altitude (m)	180	180	180	220	170	150
Habitat	Pond, adjacent to ricefields	Pond, ±50 ha	Ricefield, alongside lake, ±20 ha	Roadside pond	New pond, 200 m ² , in forest clearing	Roadside canal, 300 m ²
Predominant cultivated variety	Not identified	Idom—cultivated for 20 yr, non-glutinous	Kao chao malee — slightly improved variety from Thailand	Iloupe - cultivated for several years	Not identified	RD6—an improved glutinous variety
Wild species	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	<i>O. nivara</i>	Not identified	Not identified
Hybrid features	More vigorous than wild rices	Backcrossed to cultivated rice	Backcrossed to cultivated rice	More vigorous than wild rices	Uniform, mimicking cultivated rice	Segregating for awn and glume traits
Remarks	Wild, with some intermediate types	Wild and weedy forms	Cultivated and weedy forms, wild forms nearby	Wild, with some intermediate types	Weedy form only	Wild, with some intermediate types

From the four populations we studied, the predominant rice varieties cultivated nearby are most likely to have hybridized with the wild species (see table). In two populations we could not identify either the wild species or the probable cultivated varieties. The intermediate forms had characters from both wild and cultivated rice. Until flowering, the intermediate forms resembled the cultivated forms for most morphological characters (culm size, leaf blade length

and width, and tillering) and in gross morphology. After flowering, however, their panicle and grain characters made them easy to distinguish. The intermediate forms also produced panicles and grains that resembled the wild forms—slightly larger than the wild forms, but considerably smaller than the cultivated forms. We also observed some of the dominant characters of cultivated rice, such as leaf sheath pigmentation. All the wild forms had long green bristles

(absent in the cultivated forms), and the intermediate forms had red or purple bristles of intermediate length. We observed segregation for bristle length and color in the Samakhixai population, and for awn and grain characters in the Nongpin population.

The weedy forms are useful for identifying desirable segregates combining traits from the wild and cultivated forms. It may be worthwhile to screen the weedy forms for stress resistance traits. ■

Genetics

Genetics of anthocyanin pigmentation in rice

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We studied the inheritance of anthocyanin pigmentation of leaf sheaths in rice for eight crosses during the 1995 wet season at CRRI. Three deepwater varieties, Jalamagna, NDGR 410, and Kariawa (with purple pigmentation), and two tall indica varieties (TK deepstraw 34-774 and Khao Y Khao) were crossed during the 1993 wet season. Seeds of the parents, their F_1 s, and F_2 s were sown in small trays (50 × 40 cm). Twenty seedlings of each parent, 15 seedlings of each F_1 , and about 200-300 seedlings of each F_2 population were uprooted and washed 15 d after sowing. The frequency of plants with purple leaf sheaths was determined.

All F_1 seedlings of crosses between purple and green parents had purple pigmentation like that of the purple parent, indicating the trait's dominance (see table). F_2 populations of crosses between purple and green parents segregated into a 9 purple-7 green ratio, implying that two dominant complementary genes control purple pigmentation. F_1 and F_2 plants from two purple parents were all purple, and those from two green parents were all green.

Behavior of parents, F_1 , and F_2 with respect to purple pigmentation (15 d after seeding).

	Plants tested (no.)	Observed frequency		Expected ratio of purple to green	χ^2	P
		Purple (%)	Green (%)			
Parents						
Khao Y khao	20	0	20			
TK deep straw 34-774	20	0	20			
Jalamagna	20	20	0			
NDGR410	20	20	0			
Kariawa	20	20	0			
F_1						
Khao Y khao/Jalamagna	15	15	0			
Khao Y khao/NDGR 410	15	15	0			
Khao Y khao/Kariawa	15	15	0			
TK deep straw 34-774/Jalamagna	15	15	0			
TK deep straw 34-774/NDGR 410	15	15	0			
TK deep straw 34-774/Kariawa	15	15	0			
Jalamagna/NDGR 410	15	15	0			
Khao Y khao/TKdeep straw 34-774	15	0	15			
F_2						
Khao Y khao/Jalamagna	255	140	115	143.4:111.6 (9:7)	0.19	0.50-0.75
Khao Y khao/NDGR 410	276	158	118	155.3:120.8 (9:7)	0.11	0.50-0.75
Khao Y khao/Kariawa	266	151	115	149.6:116.4 (9:7)	0.03	0.75-0.90
TK deep straw 34-774/Jalamagna	226	120	106	127.1: 98.9 (9:7)	0.91	0.25-0.50
TK deep straw 34-774/NDGR 410	287	173	114	161.4:125.6 (9:7)	1.89	0.10-0.25
TK deep straw 34-774/Kariawa	328	201	127	184.5:143.5 (9:7)	3.37	0.05-0.10
Jalamagna/NDGR 410	305	305	0	-	-	-
Khao Y khao/TK deep straw 34-774	250	0	250	-	-	-

The data are consistent with the two dominant complementary genes for anthocyanin pigmentation of leaf sheath at the seedling stage. Purple pigmentation occurred when both genes were present; the absence of either or both resulted in green pigmentation like that in the green parents. ■

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